

**Training, Research Access and Connectivity for EHRI-BE
(TRACE-BE)
ESFRI-FED Programme**

Deliverable 5.1.1

Communication and dissemination plan

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Abstract (for dissemination)	The 'Training Research Access and Connectivity for EHRI-BE' (TRACE-BE) project, which is funded as part of the Belgian Science Policy Office's ESFRI-FED programme, aims to (1) to consolidate the Belgian State Archives' position within the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI) by stimulating and facilitating archival-based national and transnational research on the Holocaust and (2) contribute to the further development of EHRI's Belgian national node, EHRI-BE. The following deliverable outlines a communication and dissemination plan for TRACE-BE's four-year runtime, identifies longer-term communication tools and strategies that align with those of EHRI-ERIC for EHRI-BE, and considers the Belgian State Archives' role in the development and maintenance of these once the TRACE-BE comes to an end.
Management Summary	(required if the deliverable exceeds more than 25 pages) [Max. 500 words]

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	4
2	TRACE-BE's main communication objectives	5
3	Stakeholder analysis and audiences	6
3.1	Speaking the stakeholders' language(s).....	8
4	Key messages.....	8
5	Aligning communication activities	9
5.1	TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE and EHRI-ERIC.....	9
5.2	TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE and the Belgian State Archives	10
6	Communication tools and channels	10
6.1	EHRI-BE website	10
6.2	Social media	11
6.3	Contact database and newsletter	11
6.4	Document blog.....	11
7	Visual identity	12
7.1	Publicity materials and press kit.....	12
8	Events	12
9	Project resources	13
10	Personal data protection	13
11	Monitoring and evaluation	13

1 Introduction

Since 2010 and over the course of five European-funded projects, the Belgian State Archives (SAB) has been a partner of the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI). EHRI advances transnational research, remembrance, and education by addressing the field's hallmark challenge: the wide dispersal of sources and expertise across Europe and beyond. To achieve its goals, EHRI brings together the most important Holocaust collection holders and research institutions as well as specialists in the digital humanities within its distributed research infrastructure. As the main collection holding institution of Holocaust-related archives in Belgium, the SAB's participation in EHRI is crucial to this research infrastructure's efforts to secure seamless access to all sources and expertise from across Europe and beyond that are relevant to the study of the Holocaust. The SAB has made valuable contributions to foundation-laying EHRI objectives throughout three integration activities projects (EHRI 1,2,3) and two INFRADEV projects (EHRI-Preparatory Phase Project, EHRI-Implementation Phase Project).¹ Its contributions to identifying and integrating data, defining an EHRI privacy policy, transforming EHRI into a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), and defining EHRI-ERIC's scientific strategy rank among the most significant. Crucially for the Belgian context, this federal scientific institution, along with Kazerne Dossin, has also been instrumental in the establishment of EHRI's Belgian national node consortium, EHRI-BE. Made up of 14 partners, EHRI-BE covers the federal level and all federated entities of Belgium, the three official languages and a range of research, archival, digital humanities and cultural heritage profiles that contribute to EHRI-ERIC's service infrastructure.

The SAB's current EHRI-related project 'Training Research Access and Connectivity for EHRI-BE' (TRACE-BE) differs from the EHRI projects cited above as it is not supported by European funds, but federal Belgian funding as part of the Belgian Science Policy Office's [ESFRI-FED programme](#). This programme is designed specifically to support the participation of Belgian *federal* scientific institutions in ESFRI research infrastructures. TRACE-BE is coordinated by the SAB's fourth operational directorate, the Study and Documentation Centre for War and Contemporary Society (CegeSoma), and also involves Kazerne Dossin, another long-term Belgian EHRI partner. The overarching aims of TRACE-BE are: (1) consolidate the SAB's position within EHRI by stimulating and facilitating archival-based national and transnational research on the Holocaust and (2) contribute to the further development of EHRI-BE.

The following communication and dissemination plan is the first of three deliverables that will be produced as part of Task 5.1 'Project communication and dissemination', which is one of several tasks that make up TRACE-BE's fifth work package, 'Valorisation, dissemination and exploitation of results'. Given the nature of TRACE-BE's objectives, the aim of this task is not only to propose a communication plan for the project's four-year runtime, but also to identify long-term communication tools and strategies that align with those of EHRI-ERIC for EHRI-BE, as well as outline the SAB's role in the development and maintenance of these once the project comes to an end. In the case of this specific deliverable, the opening sections consider the main principles underpinning TRACE-BE's and EHRI-BE's communication activities, outlining the main objectives (section 2); identifying stakeholders (section 3); listing the key messages (section 4); and addressing how TRACE-BE and EHRI-BE communication may be aligned with that of the wider EHRI consortium (section 5). The document then turns to the practical application of the communication plan, identifying appropriate communication tools and channels (section 6), as well as discussing EHRI-BE's visual identity (section 7) and planned events (section 8). The deliverable then ends with an overview of resources TRACE-BE can commit to communication (section 9), the project's approach to personal

¹ For more on EHRI's projects and associated deliverables, see <https://www.ehri-project.eu/project-overview/>.

data processed in relation to its communication activities (section 10) and how the various proposed communication initiatives can be monitored and evaluated (section 11).

Several deliverables produced during the EHRI Implementation Phase project – namely the ‘Project dissemination plan’, the ‘Report on project dissemination’ and the ‘Report on long-term branding and marketing strategy for EHRI-ERIC’² – have served as inspiration for this plan, as have the communication toolkits provided by the ERIC Forum and the RI-VIS project.³ Additional feedback has also been sought from staff responsible for or with experience in communication at EHRI-ERIC’s central hub, other EHRI national nodes, Kazerne Dossin, and the CegeSoma.

2 TRACE-BE’s main communication objectives

Given that the overarching mission of an organisation or project sets the framework for any communication plan, it is important to restate TRACE-BE’s objectives, which are:

1. Significantly reinforce and enhance the contribution of the Belgian State Archives – the main collection holding institution of Holocaust-related archives in Belgium – to EHRI-ERIC’s services and activities for the benefit of its user communities.
2. Contribute to the full implementation and governance of the Belgian National Node of EHRI-ERIC (EHRI-BE) and integrate the Belgian State Archives in the activities of the National Coordinators Committee of EHRI-ERIC and EHRI-ERIC more generally.

It is worth drawing attention to the second objective here, with its reference to achieving the full implementation of EHRI-BE. This element implies that the following communication plan should serve as a basis for a longer-term communication strategy for EHRI’s Belgian node. With that in mind, it is also useful to consider EHRI-BE’s mission of supporting EHRI by:

- representing Belgian institutions active in the field of documentation, commemoration and research on the Holocaust;
- establishing and developing a strong and varied research consortium;
- exchanging and sharing expertise on digital developments and connecting resources through a state-of-the-art digital infrastructure;
- disseminating, implementing and developing innovative digital research tools; and
- offering training opportunities for researchers, archivists and other specialists.

In order to help TRACE-BE and EHRI-BE attain their objectives, the aim of the communication activities that will be undertaken throughout the project is to raise awareness about the SAB and the wider EHRI-BE; build a varied and committed user community primarily based in Belgium; inform users of SAB and EHRI-BE resources and tools; promote training and networking opportunities; and amplify the project’s and EHRI-BE’s scientific and non-scientific results and outputs. Achieving these objectives will require addressing key messages to specific stakeholders via the appropriate communication channels, and each of these will be discussed in the following sections.

² P. Drenth, K. Freise, J. Hlavinka, R. Pistol, R. Popa, *Deliverable 7.1: Project Dissemination Plan*, Deliverable 7.3 Report on project dissemination’, July 2024, <https://www.ehri-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/D7.1-Project-dissemination-plan.pdf>; P. Drenth, K. Freise, R. Speck, J. Hlavinka, J. Bronec, R. Popa, M. Brandl, *Deliverable 7.4: Report on long-term branding and marketing strategy for EHRI-ERIC*, July 2025, <https://www.ehri-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/D7.4-Report-on-long-term-branding-and-marketing-strategy-for-EHRI-ERIC.pdf>.

³ *ERIC Forum Toolkit: Communication*, <https://www.eric-forum.eu/toolkit/communication/social-media-strategy/>, accessed 3 February 2026; *RI-VIS Communication Toolkit for Research Infrastructures*, <https://toolkit.ri-vis.eu/home>, accessed 3 February 2026.

3 Stakeholder analysis and audiences

In order to ensure the efficacy of this communication plan, it is necessary to identify the relevant stakeholders, i.e. those people, groups or organisations that affect or will be affected by TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE's strategy.⁴ Given the overlap between EHRI's and the Belgian national node's objectives and activities, EHRI-IP 'Deliverable 7.4: Report on long-term branding and marketing strategy for EHRI-ERIC' has served as a useful starting point for identifying both internal and external TRACE-BE and EHRI-BE stakeholders, the majority of which are based in Belgium and cover the federal level, the regions and the different communities. Internal stakeholders include:

- EHRI-BE partners
- Belgian Science Policy Office
- TRACE-BE's Follow-Up committee
- EHRI-ERIC

External stakeholders are:

- Users
- Other EHRI bodies
- Non-EHRI-BE institutions/organisations with overlapping interests
- Funders
- Policy makers
- Press
- General public

The following table describes these stakeholders, maps their interest in TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE, indicates their importance for the project and Belgian national node and notes the main communication channels that will be used to engage them.

Stakeholder	Examples	Main areas of interest in TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE	Importance	Main communication channels
Internal stakeholders				
Various TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE partners + plus members of advisory bodies	Managers, research and technical staff, other support staff	Current TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE services and activities, planning and continued development of the Belgian national node. Events, innovations, new tools and methods. Access to best practices, guidelines and training	Very high	Email Internal meetings EHRI-BE website Social media Newsletters Publications Events

⁴ L. Vincenz-Donnelly, R. Pieruschka, N. Haley, *RI-VIS D4.2: Communication Strategy*, October 2020, p. 3.

External stakeholders				
Users	Researchers, archivists, collection specialists, university and other educators, curators based in Belgium and abroad	Simplified and comprehensive access to TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE services and activities	Very high	EHRI-BE website Social media Newsletters PR material Publications Events Other EHRI websites
Other EHRI bodies	Other national nodes, working groups, regional groupings, governance and advisory boards	TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE services and activities, planning and continued development of the Belgian national node. Events, innovations, new tools and methods. Access to best practices, guidelines and training	Very high	Meetings EHRI-BE website Social media Newsletters Publications Events
Non-EHRI-BE partners with overlapping interests	Includes potential future partner institutions or organisations active in the fields of Holocaust studies, education, remembrance, digital humanities and archives, as well as other SSH research infrastructures	Cooperation with TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE Use of resources, tools provided by TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE Development of the Belgian national node. Activities/events, innovations, new tools and methods.	High to very high	EHRI-BE website Social media Newsletters Publications PR material Events

Funders	Funding bodies, including European and Belgian bodies at federal, regional and community levels	Learning of TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE's activities and achievements	Medium to high	EHRI-BE website Publications PR material Social media
Policy makers	At the Belgian level: federal and community ministries	TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE resources and tools that may be used in programmes that discuss the Holocaust and antisemitism and promote human rights and diversity.	Medium to high	EHRI-BE website Publications Press releases Events Social media
Press	Traditional and non-traditional media outlets active Belgium's different regions	Contextual information about the Holocaust in relation to Belgium or a particular Belgian region	Medium	EHRI-BE website Publications Press releases Events Social media
General public		Learning about the Holocaust, researching family/local history	Medium	EHRI-BE website Social media Events

3.1 Speaking the stakeholders' language(s)

While the official working language of the wider EHRI consortium is English, sufficient knowledge of this language cannot be taken for granted among EHRI-BE stakeholders based in Belgium, a country with three official languages: Dutch, French and German. Where relevant and feasible, the TRACE-BE team is committed to providing translations of its website pages, social media posts and newsletters in order to reach the largest audience possible. Translation support can be sought in-house, i.e. from the Belgian State Archives, as well as through subscription to advanced translation platforms, such as DeepL.

4 Key messages

Given that the TRACE-BE project and EHRI-BE more generally have a finite amount of resources to dedicate to communication, it is essential that any communication-related activities are efficient and encourage maximum stakeholder engagement. This will be achieved through the dissemination of key messages that are tailored to the specific needs and interests of the different stakeholder groups discussed above. The key messages outlined below are largely based on those from EHRI-ERIC's long-term communication and dissemination plan to ensure consistency with the wider research infrastructure's messaging,

although they have been adapted to reflect the targeted aims of the TRACE-BE project and the (naturally) narrower scope of EHRI-BE's activities.⁵

The key messages that will be shared with different stakeholders throughout the TRACE-BE project are:

- The Belgian State Archives are the main Holocaust-related collection holding institution in Belgium and, working in close collaboration with other EHRI-BE partners, it plays a significant role in the development of EHRI's Belgian national node as well as that of EHRI-ERIC itself.
- EHRI-BE aims to establish an innovative national node linked to a diverse user community which, in turn, will build, inform and take advantage of the services and activities offered by this national node.
- EHRI-BE connects fragmented and dispersed sources and researchers located in Belgium with sources and researchers throughout EHRI's wider network.
- EHRI-BE contributes to the development of digital tools and methods that advance the digital transformation of Holocaust research and archiving.
- EHRI-BE builds bridges through fellowship and training programmes and by organising and participating in conferences, seminars and workshops in Belgium and beyond.
- EHRI-BE brings together researchers and data from across Belgium and elsewhere and enables the transfer of knowledge between Belgian communities and EHRI partners abroad.
- Collaboration with EHRI allows EHRI-BE to contribute to innovations that encourage new approaches to Holocaust research and archiving, particularly in the realms of transnational and comparative research.
- EHRI-BE's work has relevance beyond its specific research context and can inform similar initiatives across the humanities and social sciences.
- EHRI-BE helps fight Holocaust denial and distortion, antisemitism, racism and xenophobia by providing scientific expertise and infrastructural support.
- EHRI-BE is committed to mobilising its resources, network and expertise to provide scientific input and support to antisemitism-related policymaking when required.

These key messages will be reviewed at the halfway point of the TRACE-BE project (January 2028) and once again when the project comes to an end in January 2030. They will also be discussed in light of any guidance on messaging that EHRI's Central Hub will issue in the future.

5 Aligning communication activities

5.1 TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE and EHRI-ERIC

The communication team at EHRI's central hub arranges monthly meetings with national node staff. The aim of these meetings is to coordinate approaches to promoting EHRI services and activities; ensure consistency in EHRI marketing and branding; and exchange best practices between national nodes and the central hub. Prior to the commencement of the TRACE-BE project, this meeting was attended by one or both members of EHRI-BE's national coordination team representing the Belgian State Archives (SAB) and Kazerne Dossin. Given that TRACE-BE has an entire work package dedicated to communication, responsibility for attending this monthly meeting will fall to the project researcher(s), although other representatives from EHRI-BE may still be welcome to attend should they wish and if they are actively involved in EHRI-BE's communication activities.

⁵ See P. Drenth, et al., *Deliverable 7.4*, p. 16–17.

5.2 TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE and the Belgian State Archives

TRACE-BE project members will be in regular contact with the communication staff of the SAB, including the communications officer of the Study and Documentation Centre for War and Contemporary Society (CegeSoma), in order to share best practices and benefit from the SAB's and CegeSoma's already well-established communication channels.

6 Communication tools and channels

TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE's current communication channels and tools include a Belgian national node website and publicity materials. These were developed over the course of previous EHRI projects as part of the work undertaken by the Belgian State Archives (SAB) and Kazerne Dossin to establish the Belgian national node, with additional support – including templates and branding – provided by EHRI. At the time, the website and publicity materials were sufficient for EHRI-BE's needs given the limited amount of resources that could be dedicated to the Belgian national node's communication activities. TRACE-BE, however, has far broader communication objectives, and this means that the website will require further development, the publicity materials will likely require updating at some stage and new communication channels must be opened to reach as many of TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE's stakeholder groups as possible.

What follows is a summary of the communication tools and channels that will be mobilised during the TRACE-BE's runtime. In most cases, these will be managed directly by project and Belgian national node members. Responsibility for validating what appears on these tools and in these channels lies with EHRI-BE's national coordination team. It is also worthwhile pointing out that TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE will have the opportunity to communicate its key messages through 'secondary' tools and channels, such as those managed by the SAB, the Study and Documentation Centre for War and Contemporary Society (CegeSoma), EHRI's central hub and other national nodes.

6.1 EHRI-BE website

The Belgian national node's website was developed during the EHRI Implementation Phase project and is based on a template provided by EHRI's central hub to all of its national nodes.⁶ It aims to engage all EHRI-BE stakeholder groups by providing information on EHRI-BE's objectives, activities, partners, services and contact details, as well as the latest EHRI-related news. It also contains links to EHRI's central website and resources, as well as social media accounts – Facebook, X, LinkedIn and Bluesky – run by the EHRI central hub. To ensure that the widest audience possible is reached by the site, its main pages have been translated into Belgium's three official languages – Dutch, French and German – as well as the English, which is the working language of EHRI.

A degree of ongoing support for the technical management and branding of the website is provided by EHRI's central hub, but the responsibility for updating the content on the site has largely fallen to the SAB and Kazerne Dossin (although other EHRI-BE partners have been requested to provide descriptions of their institutions/organisations). It is foreseen that this arrangement will continue throughout TRACE-BE, with the additional aim of providing news updates on a more regular basis than previously. Certain embedded links will also be changed so they redirect visitors to specific EHRI-BE social media accounts once these have been created (see below), as opposed to those managed by EHRI's central hub.

⁶ For a technical description of this template, see M. Bryant, H. García González, J. Meerwald, F. Miez, *Deliverable 4.3: Report on technological development*, January 2026, <https://www.ehri-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/D4.3-Report-on-technological-development.pdf>, p. 6.

6.2 Social media

At the time of writing, TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE has no direct presence on social media. One of the main objectives of TRACE-BE's Work Package 5 is to activate and regularly update relevant social media accounts to valorise the achievements and contributions of EHRI-BE's different partners, particularly those of the SAB, and inform followers of events and training opportunities. Based on the experiences of EHRI's central hub, other EHRI national nodes and the CegeSoma, as well as the resources available to the TRACE-BE team, it has been decided that accounts will be set up on Facebook and LinkedIn in the name of EHRI-BE. Both of these platforms offer the possibility of engaging a large number of individuals and, more importantly, a wide variety of stakeholders, ranging from professional users to the general public. Furthermore, both EHRI and the CegeSoma are well established and have attracted thousands of followers on these platforms, which means there is considerable scope for cross-promotion.

It may be decided further down the track to establish EHRI-BE on other social media platforms, after all, EHRI also has YouTube, X and Bluesky accounts and CegeSoma has recently become active on Instagram. However, in the case of YouTube and Instagram, in order for EHRI-BE to get the most out of these, it would have to post regular video and/or photo content, which is something that is not envisaged (nor budgeted for) in the TRACE-BE project. As for the microblogging platforms X and Bluesky, EHRI's central hub decided to no longer post on the former as of March 2025 after concluding that 'X is no longer a platform that aligns with our core mission and values' and, so far, it has not managed to attract as many followers as it had on X on Bluesky.

6.3 Contact database and newsletter

TRACE-BE aims to start sending quarterly newsletters to subscribers within the first year of the project. These newsletters will contain, among other things, news items covering TRACE-BE progress, developments within EHRI-BE and events, as well as communications provided by EHRI's central hub and other national nodes if these are relevant to EHRI-BE's audience.

As this will be the first time EHRI-BE launches such a campaign, the initial challenge will be building up a contact database. In the case of EHRI, its communication team has identified two types of subscribers to its newsletter: those who subscribe via the EHRI website and those who are added by the administrator after receiving a request.⁷ A similar approach to attracting subscribers can be applied to EHRI-BE, but it will require slightly adapting the EHRI-BE website so it can offer visitors the possibility of signing up to the newsletter. EHRI-BE can also directly contact its current members to encourage them to sign up and announcements on social media (EHRI-BE-managed accounts as well as those of EHRI, the CegeSoma, the SAB and Kazerne Dossin and, hopefully, EHRI-BE members) and in EHRI's and CegeSoma's own newsletters will also be used to drive up subscription numbers.

As for the platform that can be used to directly email newsletters to subscribers, a note has been drafted identifying several potential service providers that should respond to TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE's needs.

6.4 Document blog

One of the online services EHRI provides is a [document blog](#) where ideas about Holocaust-related archival documents and their presentation and interpretation using digital tools can be shared. Although this service is not managed by EHRI-BE, it is worth citing here given that one of the aims of TRACE-BE is to produce several contributions showcasing the SAB's

⁷ P. Drenth, et al., *Deliverable 7.4*, p. 21.

collections and, where relevant, those of other EHRI-BE partners to an international audience. These contributions will increase the visibility of Belgian archives and ensure that they are adequately represented in the wider EHRI network.

7 Visual identity

EHRI has established and maintained a strong visual identity throughout its different projects and has propagated this identity throughout the distributed research infrastructure, thereby ensuring that national nodes are clearly associated with the wider organisation. EHRI's visual identity has recently undergone an update to ensure greater consistency throughout the ERIC and its national nodes and, as part of this update, EHRI-BE has been supplied with a raft of materials, including language-specific EHRI-BE logos, PowerPoint and social media templates, and images for use on roll-up banners, among others. EHRI-BE will use these new branding materials for its various communication channels and activities, but it will also be necessary to ensure that the institutions actively involved in the TRACE-BE project – the Belgian State Archives (SAB), the Study and Documentation Centre for War and Contemporary Society (CegeSoma) and Kazerne Dossin – are visibly acknowledged through the inclusion of their logos where appropriate. Specific TRACE-BE communications should also acknowledge the Belgian Science Policy Office, which funds TRACE-BE through its ESFRI-FED programme.

7.1 Publicity materials and press kit

As noted above, the SAB and Kazerne Dossin have already developed certain publicity materials for EHRI-BE – a roll-up banner and flyers – during previous EHRI projects. These materials are consistent with EHRI's colour palette and are still valid as far as members are concerned. However, it is possible that they will require updating at some stage of the TRACE-BE project – e.g. with EHRI's new brand logo – or additional materials may be created to engage different stakeholders. In its report on EHRI's marketing strategy, the EHRI communication team has indicated that it can 'provide support to national nodes in their efforts to produce specific publicity materials... with the object of maintaining a unified (visual) identity' and this has already been demonstrated by the new brand materials the central hub has shared with its national nodes, including EHRI-BE.⁸ Moreover, documentation and templates provided by EHRI-ERIC, such as the 'EHRI in a nutshell' document, adapted for a Belgian audience (e.g. translated into the country's official languages) will form the basis of an EHRI-BE press kit that will be put together during the TRACE-BE project.

8 Events

A number of targeted and public events have been planned as part of TRACE-BE to stimulate Holocaust research based on collections located in Belgium (particularly those belonging to the Belgian State Archives), enhance cooperation between EHRI-BE partners and share results with the wider public. These events include seminars aimed at junior researchers; interactive workshops for doctoral and postdoctoral students; information days for the general public; and a TRACE-BE fellowship programme aimed at encouraging researchers from abroad to consult and engage with SAB collections. They will be planned, delivered and evaluated according to the user engagement guidelines laid down by EHRI and adapted to the Belgian context to ensure they are effective and consistent with other events organised throughout the distributed research infrastructure.⁹

⁸ P. Drenth, et al., *Deliverable 7.4*, p. 24.

⁹ See E. Moscovitz, J. Meerwald, K. Freise, R. Speck, M. Frankl, *Deliverable 4.1: User Engagement Guidelines*, February 2025, <https://www.ehri-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/D4.1-User-engagement-guidelines.pdf>, p. 7–11.

9 Project resources

To make up for the relatively limited nature of EHRI-BE communication prior to now, the TRACE-BE project places a particular emphasis on communication with one-fifth of the project's total person months being earmarked for Work Package 5 tasks. The majority is dedicated to the organisation of events and the TRACE-BE fellowship programme (see section 8), while the rest primarily cover updates to current communication tools and the expansion into new communication channels (see section 6). Kazerne Dossin will also provide a limited number of person months to help with upgrades associated with EHRI-BE's website. Overall, the number of person months set aside for TRACE-BE's communication work should be sufficient to meet the project's specific targets (see section 10).

As for communication-related costs, a small amount of the project's overhead budget has been set aside to cover subscriptions to relevant services such as a marketing platform to distribute the EHRI-BE newsletter and a translation platform, as well as the printing of promotional material and the hosting of the planned events.

10 Personal data protection

In order to effectively undertake certain tasks outlined above – for instance the fellowship programme, seminars and workshops – a minimum of participants' data must be processed including name, surname, institutional affiliation, email address and responses to calls and/or surveys, but no sensitive information will be processed. Analytics data from TRACE-BE's different communication channels may also be stored for monitoring and evaluation (see section below), but this will be anonymised and visitors to the websites will have the option to decide whether their activity is tracked. This approach is in line with the [Belgian State Archives' personal data protection policy](#) and [EHRI-ERIC's general personal data protection policy](#).

11 Monitoring and evaluation

The table below outlines the communication targets set at the beginning of the TRACE-BE project.

Communication channel/activity	Timing/Quantity	Audience	Purpose	Content
EHRI-BE website	Throughout BUT main feature and design update by M12	All stakeholders	Raise awareness Inform Promote	Regularly updated information on TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE (including opportunities, results)
Social media	Accounts activated in M4, regular updates thereafter	All stakeholders	Raise awareness Inform Engage Promote	Regularly updated information on TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE (including opportunities, results)

Newsletters	M7 and then quarterly thereafter (11 in total)	All stakeholders	Inform Promote	Information about events, training opportunities and achievements
Promotional material	Certain materials already available; can be updated as necessary	Users, non-EHRI-BE partners with overlapping interests, funders	Raise awareness Promote	General information about EHRI-BE
EHRI Document Blog posts	M8, M16, M24, M32, M40, M48	Users, other EHRI bodies, non-EHRI-BE partners with overlapping interests, funders, general public	Inform Promote Engage	Showcase SAB and EHRI-BE partner collections, research and tools
TRACE-BE fellowships	Three calls to be launched in M12, M24 and M36	Users, EHRI-BE partners, other EHRI bodies, non-EHRI-BE partners with overlapping interests	Promote Engage	Quality research engaging with SAB and EHRI-BE partner collections
Seminars	M18, M30, M42	Users, EHRI-BE partners, other EHRI bodies, non-EHRI-BE partners with overlapping interests	Inform Promote Engage	Training for junior researchers
Workshops	M24, M36, M48	Users, EHRI-BE partners, other EHRI bodies, non-EHRI-BE partners with overlapping interests	Inform Promote Engage	Training for doctoral and postdoctoral researchers; testing services developed during TRACE-BE
Public outreach events	M24 and M48	All stakeholders	Raise awareness Inform Engage Promote	Present TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE, publicise project results, discuss future steps

Ensuring that the targets above are met within TRACE-BE's timeframe is a good starting point for gauging the success of the tasks carried out in the project's work package on valorisation and dissemination. However, to have a clearer idea of how effective communication has been over the course of TRACE-BE, it will also be necessary, where

possible, to monitor and evaluate the performance of the communication channels and activities cited above. Several quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) to track the performance of EHRI's communication activities were identified as fitting the RACER criteria – i.e. they are 'relevant', 'accepted' by stakeholders, 'credible', 'easy to monitor' and 'robust' – during the EHRI Implementation Phase project and these can also be applied to a certain extent in the context of TRACE-BE/EHRI-BE. They include KPIs that measure reach and engagement, e.g., followers on social media and subscribers to the newsletter; user engagement and growth online; and the level of user engagement by direct contact, e.g. at in-person events.¹⁰ The specifics of these KPIs will be further defined over the course of TRACE-BE in Work Package 5 and Work Package 4 (Task 4.3 addresses monitoring and performance management in particular), as well as through discussions with other internal stakeholders, including EHRI-BE partners and the communication team at EHRI's central hub.

¹⁰ M. Haultain-Gall, A. Babeş-Fruchter, D. Luyten, R. Speck, F. Uiterwaal, K. Freise, H. García González, *Deliverable 2.3: Handbook on EHRI-ERIC Management Guidelines with workable systems for risk, quality and performance management*, January 2026, <https://www.ehri-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/D2.3-Handbook-on-EHRI-ERIC-Management-Guidelines-with-workable-systems-for-risk-quality-and-performance-management.pdf>, p. 14; P. Drenth et al., *Deliverable 7.4*, p. 26; K. Freise, R. Speck, J. Meerwald, M. Frankl, M. Brandl, *Deliverable 7.2: Social-economic impact assessment framework including impact case studies*, January 2026, <https://www.ehri-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/D7.2-SEIA-framework-including-impact-case-studies.pdf>, p. 21.